

Corrigenda zu
 „Maas, Philipp André. *Samādhipāda. Das erste Kapitel des
 Pātañjalayogaśāstra zum ersten Mal kritisch ediert*. Aachen: Shaker, 2006
 (Studia Indologica Universitatis Halensis)
 (Geisteskultur Indiens. Texte und Studien 9)“.

Philipp A. Maas

Seit der Publikation der ersten kritischen Edition des Samādhipāda des *Pātañjalayogaśāstra* im Jahre 2006, sind mir eine Reihe von Fehlern in dieser Arbeit aufgefallen, die gemäß folgender Liste zu korrigieren sind.

Die Corrigenda betreffen vor allem Flüchtigkeitsfehler und Einträge im zweiten Apparat der kritischen Edition, der Lesarten aus den Druckausgaben verzeichnet. Bedingt durch die Konvertierung des Manuskripts in eine für mich (damals) neue Software, sind Minderheitenlesarten des kritisch edierten Textes in einer Reihe von Fällen nicht als Abweichungen von Text aller verfügbaren Druckausgaben verzeichnet worden.

Seite, Zeile	lies	statt
vii, 23	française	Française
vii, 23	3.2	3.2.
xi, 13	française	Française
xii, 13	<i>patañjalim</i>	<i>patañjalim</i>
xii, 19	<i>Sarvadarśanasamgraha</i>	<i>Ṣaddarśanasamgraha</i>
xii, 25	<i>Philosophy</i> , Vol. 1,	<i>Philosophy</i>
xiii, fn. 18	J. BRONKHORST	BRONKHORST
xvi, fn 34	J. BRONKHORST	J.BRONKHORST
xviii, fn. 48	GBh 107	GBh 70
xxxiii, 6	22 Handschriften	20 Handschriften
lii, fn. 10	Durchschnittlich	Druchschnittlich
liv, 1	française	Française
lxi, 20	(662)	(622)
lxiii, fn. 2	Doppelpunkte	Duppelpunkte
lxviii, 11	Alt-Bengali-	Alt-Bengali
lxix, fn. 5	104	102
lxix, fn. 6	105	103
lxxi, 22	M ^g	Ma ^g
lxxi, 22	M ^g	Ma ^g
lxxiv, 13	50.10	-50.10
lxxv, 38	1108	11088
lxxvii, 32	C 2004/2	C 204/2
lxxviii, 4	française	Française
1, 19	hariḥ śrī-	namaḥ śrī-
1, 17	śrīmatkalyāṇa	śrīmat kalyāṇa

1, 17	śrīmatde	śrīmat de
1, 21	$My^{12} Pv^{n3}$	Pv^{n3}
2, 5	$(-B^t My^{12}$	$(-B^t$
2, 5	<i>tilge: yas om yas My^{12}</i>	
2, 10	P^n	$My^N P^n$
4, 8	*rodhe	*rodha
4, 15	dhaḥ My^{13a}	dhaḥ My^{1a}
4, 31	2.2 cittam] sarvaśabdāgrahaṇāt samprajñāto 'pi yoga ity ākhyāyate cittam E	2.2
5, 40	5 rajomātrayānuviddham] anuviddham rajomātrayā E	5
5, 41	7 tat] tat param E	7
6, 36	śuddhānantāsattvā puruṣātmikā seyam] śuddhā cānantā ca sattvaguṇātmikā ceyam E 11	11
7, 25	-bhāvaḥ] bhāva iti E 2	2
8, 26	-aviśiṣṭaḥ] aviśiṣṭavṛtīḥ	-aviśiṣṭaḥ]
10, 36	5 akliṣṭappravāhapatitāḥ kliṣṭāḥ] om. E	5
11, 32	6 akliṣṭāḥ] akliṣṭā bhavanti E	6
13, 35	darśaiṣyāmaḥ] upapādayiṣyāmaḥ E 6	6
13, 36	J^E nivṛtto] vyāvṛtto E	J^E
14, 36	viplavate] plavate E 8.2 'bhūtārthaviśayatvāt] bhūtārthaviśayatvāt pramāṇasya E 3	8.3
15, 32	5 sā ca] seyam E -parvāvidyā] pravā bhavaty avidyā E	5
17, 36	Bh^L 7 gamyate] avagamyate E	Bh^L
18, 40	Bh^L 8 smṛttayas] smṛttayaś ca E	Bh^L
19, 30	10.9 nirodhavyā] nirodhavyeti E 11.2	11.2
19, 33	P^{E2} grāhyagrahaṇātmikām] grāhyagrahaṇubhayātmikām E	P^{E2}
20, 38	jāgraty] jāgratsamaye tv E 7-smartavyā] smartavyeti E	7
21, 27	nirodhavyā vṛttayaḥ] vṛttayo nirodhavyā E samādhir bhavaty]	samādhir bhavaty]
22, 33	4 -nimnā¹] viṣayanimnā sā E	4
23, 26	3 sādhanānuṣṭhānam] tatsādhanānuṣṭhānam E	14.1
25, 19	viṣaye T^n	viṣaye 123
25, 29	2 -darśī] darśī viraktaḥ E	2
27, 8	-vṛtteḥ]	vṛtteḥ]
28, 26	kalpate	kakalpate
28, 39	-mātraḥ	-mātraḥ]
29, 30	E 19.1 upāya-²] tatropāya E	E
30, 26	$Bo2^{E6}$ devā bhavanti] devānām bhavapratyayaḥ E ◇ te saṃskāra-] te hi svasaṃskāra E	$Bo2^{E6}$
31, 9	Pv^{n3}	Pv^{n3}
33, 26	tato 'pi	to pi
33, 29	ca] ca bhavaṭīti E 22.2	22.2
36, 13	vyapadiśyante K^{n2}	vyapadiśyante $K^b K^{n2}$
38, 38	aiśvaryāntareṇaātīśayate] aiśvaryāntareṇa tad atīśayate E ◇ -muktam]	-muktam]
41, 28	parama ṛṣir] parama ṛṣir E	11
42, 29	vācyavācakatavam E sthitam] avasthitam E	vācyavācakatavam E
47, 36	vijñānam E dhātu-] dhāturasakaraṇa E	vijñānam E
52, 35	VI^E ; pravāhena $AI^E Bh^E Bo^E P^E V^E (-VI^E)$	$P^E VI^E$; pravāhena $AI^E Bh^E Bo^E V^E (-VI^E)$
52, 38	12 -vāhī]	12 vāhī]
52, 38	pratyayapravāhī E cittānupak]ptiḥ] cittānupapattiḥ E	pratyayapravāhī E
55, 29	23 hi] ca E 24	24
56, 7	YVi	YVi , 119
56, 17	$(-B^s Pv^{n3})$	$(-B^s Pv^{n1} Pv^{n3})$
61, 13	Pv^{n4}	Pv^{n4} }
65, 37	nididarśaiṣyayedam sūtram pravavṛte] ucyate E 3	3
70, 33	7 -vikalpa] jñānavikalpa E 8	8

70, 34	tac tac ca E 10	10
71, 31	śabda E śrutānumāna-] śrutānumānajñana E	śabda E
72, 22	viśeṣā+	viśeṣā+
72, 33	<i>V4^E</i> -upakramo upakramo hy E	<i>V4^E</i>
72, 33	...-viśeṣātmāmbanam- 	... 'ṇu-
77, 18	<i>M^S</i> (<i>pc</i>)	<i>M^S</i> (<i>ac</i>)
77, 39	kiṃca kiṃ tu E 7	7
80, 29	<i>GDhp</i>	<i>GDhp</i>
81, 33	<i>V2^E</i> 49.1 śrutānumānābhyām śrutānumānaprajñābhyām E	<i>V2^E</i>
81, 33	viśeṣārthavattvāt viśeṣārthatvāt E 49.2	49.2
82, 28	<i>M^S</i> ;	<i>M^S</i>
83, 32	9 chrutānumānābhyām chrutānumānaprajñābhyām E	9
83, 32	viśeṣārthavattvād viśeṣārthatvād E sā	sā
84, 36	-prajñāprabhavaṃ <i>om.</i> E 4	4
84, 40	<i>V1^E</i> te na te prajñākṛtāḥ E	<i>V1^E</i>
85, 26	na <i>om.</i> E 10	10
87, 7	nivartate 	cittam
90, fn. 8	Z.B.	z.B
90, fn. 9	Z.B.	z.B.
110, 15	51.4	51.5
115, 17	The Kashmir	Kashmir
115, 17	33)	32)
115, 30	1895]).	1895].
116, 40	Poona 1962	Bombay 1962
118, 19	<i>Vākyapādīya</i>	<i>Vākyapādīya</i>
118, 22	<i>Vākyapādīya</i>	<i>Vākyapādīya</i>
118, 25	<i>Vākyapādīya</i>	<i>Vākyapādīya</i>
121, 35	BURNELL,	BURNELL
121, 35	Palace at Tanjore	Palace of Tanjore
122	Korrigiere die vertauschte Reihenfolge der Einträge POLEMAN und NAMBIAR	
124, 2	Kl. (1930),	Kl.,
125, 25	française	Française
126, 9	<i>füge ein:</i> Whaling, Frank: „Śaṅkara and Buddhism.“ In: <i>Journal of Indian Philosophy</i> 7 (1979), pp. 1–42.	
127, 16	ein	eine
132, 3	vṛttayaḥ	vṛttaya
138, 29	tasya	tsya
151, 9	sukhadhuḥkha	suhadhuḥkha
164, 2	samskāra	samskāraś
166, fn. 5	hermeneutical	hermenteutical
171, 11	similar	similarl
171, 33	1108	11088
173, 22	C 2004/2	C 204/2
173, 33	française	Française
177, 8	sandhi	Sandhi
178, 21	characters	charakters
179, 5	121	123